

RESEARCH ON PERSONALIZED LEARNING IN SCIENCE

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In modern society increasingly affirms the Central role of the individual. What actualizes the need of substantial-technological changes in education, among which the most optimal, modern researchers are determined by processes of individualization, personalization, personification.

Keywords: education, trend, individualization, personalization, personification.

Personalized learning is a specially organized joint activity of a teacher and students within the framework of the educational process, which involves the formation of the subjective experience of students, as well as the intellectual and moral development of the individual from egocentrism to altruism, based on the psychological content of a social individual formed at the meta-ethnic level. The starting points of personalized learning are: the creation of such conditions for interaction between teacher and students, when targeted pedagogical influence is in demand by students, because has significance for the latter (social, personal, etc.); in contrast to personality-oriented concepts of learning, in personalized learning, support is placed not only on the individuality of students, but also on the typical characteristics of the teacher and students, which affects the psychological content of their social individual (in this case, there is integrity in the formation of the student's social essence in the unity of the spiritual social and socio-biological phenomena); it is always aimed not only at the formation of the "subjective experience" of the student, but also at the development of his personality from the level of egocentrism to altruism, as well as the formation of a social individual at the meta-ethnic level. Its general goal is the intellectual and moral development of students, which consists in the development of intellectual abilities (especially convergence and creativity) and the formation of social attitudes, social attitudes and moral and semantic constructs (this is consistent with the socio-psychological spheres of human integrative subjectivity); the organization of personalized learning is carried out in collective forms, thanks to which not only the personal growth of students from egocentrism to altruism is ensured, but also to some extent the problem of ambivalence of the instinctive and rational in a person is solved by establishing a "compromise" between the personality and the social individual in the process of their formation.

In modern scientific research, personalization is considered as a process: – as a result of which the subject receives an ideal representation in the life of other people and can act in public life as an individual. [1;2;3]; – transformation of external, social motivations, requirements, restrictions and social experience into elements of the structure of one's own personality (needs, aspirations, skills, knowledge, etc.) [4]; – as a result of which social relations take on a personal character [5]; – acquisition by the subject of universal, socially significant, individually unique

properties and qualities that allow him to perform a certain role in an original way, creatively build communication with other people, and actively influence their perception [6;7]; – satisfying the needs of the state, society and the individual at this historical stage in the formation and development of socially significant subjective qualities of the individual, allowing them to effectively fulfill social and professional roles [8].

A comparative analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature on the problem of personification of education allowed us to state that this concept is interpreted as: a person-oriented process, which:

- aimed at developing the abilities and interests of students [9];

- allows you to constantly monitor current changes in students, this process is aimed at maximizing the assimilation of knowledge, the formation of competencies and personality development, which is based on the desire for self-actualization and self-development [10];

- aimed at maximum social and professional development of the individual and based on the inherent desire for self-actualization and self-improvement [11];

- maximally focused on the internal activity of the student himself and his independence in educational activities [12] is a special form of organizing the educational process:

- taking into account the characteristics of individual differences of students; – based on the student's ability to realize his individual experience of cognition, educational activity, behavior [11] – in which the content, forms and methods of teaching are the subject of choice, judgment and the result of joint design activities of students and teachers [12];

- based on the student's specific self-organization of his personal educational space [13]; didactic principle, according to which: – the content and all other elements of the educational process should be determined and built on the basis of the interests, needs and aspirations of the persons involved in the educational activities;

- the student experiences "personification" in accordance with self-knowledge, mastery of his higher mental structures as a tool for solving any non-standard, creative problems [14]; one of the directions of modernization of the system of continuous professional education; factor in the development of cognitive activity of students [15]; a means of constructing an individual educational route.

The goal of learning in a personalized education model is: – formation of one’s own behavior in different areas of communication [16]; – development of a personality capable of self-realization at a creative level, psychological and pedagogical support for the subject of the educational process, formed in the paradigm “from nurturing intellectual initiative to intellectual behavior” [17].

Personalized learning is possible only with the initial orientation of teachers towards the formation or at least the formation of reflective personality qualities in the educational process, which is manifested in the student’s orientation towards the gradual internalization of actions related to the development of content, in the translation of the teaching functions of the teacher into the internal plan of action of the student. Thus, his transition to a new qualitative level of learning is carried out - self-management of his educational activities [18;19;20]. To do this, it is necessary to structure the learning process in such a way as to clearly see the results of the personal development trajectory of each student.

I.S. Kazakov identifies four activity levels: level 1 is the level of reflection (indicative level), it characterizes the student’s perception of educational material and includes such psychological processes as sensation, perception, attention, imagination, memory (as recollection), visual-figurative thinking, motive ; level 2 – comprehension: the mental function includes processing the received educational information, finding ways to solve the problem; it is characterized by such psychological processes as memory, consciousness, visual-effective or conceptual thinking, motive; level 3 – algorithmization, which is an executive function and includes an analysis of the methods used to implement the algorithm, and is characterized by such psychological processes as memory, consciousness, attention, imagination, verbal thinking, emotions, motive; level 4 – control – this is a control and correction function, is responsible for the correct execution of the result and is characterized by such psychological processes as memory, attention, thinking, speech, motive [21;22].

In general, five main stages can be distinguished in personalized learning: play, educational and gaming activities, learning, educational and labor activities, and labor.

Considering “game” as a stage of personalized learning, we should note its high creative potential. The thinking formed during this period is predominantly creative in nature and is often referred to as lateral.

Characterizing lateral thinking, one of the researchers in the psychology of creativity Ed. De Bono points out that it rebuilds familiar ideas and creates conditions for the emergence of new ones. This thinking realizes a person’s creative abilities, intuition, and sense of humor in the process of processing information and creative practical activity. In “educational and gaming” activities, lateral thinking serves as the basis for the development of rational-empirical thinking, which is always logical, consistent, unidirectional (V.V. Davydov, A.I. Savenkov, etc.).

Such thinking is the basis for the development of theoretical thinking. The latter, in fact, is determined by various sciences and develops most actively at the stage of learning. Practical thinking develops on the basis of theoretical thinking. It begins to form in educational and labor activities and actively develops in work. In essence, practical thinking is an integrative type of thinking. Based on the theoretical, it goes beyond the boundaries of individual sciences and is always tied to the field, type of work, determines the interdisciplinary meaningful integration of various sciences in practical human activity. This thinking involves finding general principles of functioning, possibly distant from each other, processes of objective reality within a specific work situation. In this case, scientific, special and “everyday” knowledge is used in conjunction. The ability to integratively use this knowledge in relation to individual aspects of work activity largely characterizes this type of thinking. In addition, practical thinking is characterized by divergence, i.e. is creative in nature. However, unlike lateral thinking, this thinking is aimed at a socially useful result. Alternative solutions to the same problem in this case are correct only in relation to the given working conditions.

Lateral technologies mainly characterize the educational and gaming stage of personalized learning. Their use is primarily aimed at supporting student creativity.

As numerous psychological studies show, the decline in creativity of younger schoolchildren compared to preschool age is one of the problems of modern primary schools. Lateral technologies are aimed at solving this problem. At the same time, they solve the problem of preparing students for reproductive educational activities. In this case, lateral and rational-empirical thinking develops in a single pedagogical system. Such technologies are mainly used in the first and second grades of primary school. A distinctive feature of lateral technologies is the use of both educational and cognitive tasks aimed at the intellectual development of students. At the same time, cognitive tasks may not be “tied” to any academic subject. Their use primarily involves the development of students’ creative abilities. Particular attention is paid to the development of the ability to put forward new, unexpected ideas that differ from the well-known, banal ones; ability to produce as many ideas as possible; abilities to detail and develop each idea through construction, etc. Problems of this type have many solutions, each of which is correct, and their conditions do not regulate the search. The learning tasks used in lateral technologies can be both convergent and divergent in nature. In the first case, the problem has a single correct solution, is subject to a certain logic and is aimed at developing logical thinking. In the second, there are several solutions to the problem, each of which can be correct depending on the given conditions.

In general, lateral technologies, ensuring the development of rational-empirical thinking in combination with lateral ones, lay the foundations for the development of theoretical thinking. They are also aimed at developing theoretical knowledge in the

subject area of study, the ability to “master” such knowledge and the skills of creative activity. Along with this, such technologies involve moral education of students through the formation of moral qualities, the establishment of “altruistic” relationships, and the creation of attitudinal behavior characteristic of collective activity.

Converging technologies define the “learning” stage of personalized learning. They are aimed largely at the formation of theoretical knowledge and skills, the development of students’ theoretical thinking. In this case, it is assumed that problems that have a single correct solution will be solved. Moreover, the answer is determined by the conditions of the problem. Problems of this kind have a rigid structure, their solution is carried out by using certain rules and algorithms. These tasks are of a convergent nature. Their use in the educational process should ensure the formation in students of such skills as the ability to analyze, synthesize, make generalizations, classify, define concepts, etc. The above technologies are used, as a rule, from the third to the sixth grade inclusive. The development of theoretical thinking within the framework of the “learning” stage is carried out during the study of general education disciplines, their basic part. The theoretical knowledge formed in this case is directly related to theoretical abstraction and generalization. At the same time, the assimilation of educational information and the emergence of concepts on this basis depends on the methods of ascent from the concrete to the abstract and from the abstract to the concrete. The latter is largely determined by the psychological types of students. The solution of educational convergent problems is largely determined by factors related to the completeness of the process of theoretical thinking.

The following factors can be taken as: 1. Establishment of a strong logical relationship between the conditions of the problem and the question posed. 2. Preliminary orientation in the conditions of the problem, suggesting the possibility of simultaneous consideration of all the constituent elements of the condition, which makes it possible to create a general scheme for solving the problem. At the same time, consideration of the constituent elements involves adding to the conditions of the problem everything that the student knows about the objects and relationships presented in the source data and using this additional knowledge to solve the problem. 3. Reformulation of the conditions of the problem and categorical generalizations. In this case, the analysis and identification of new connections occur during the verbal reformulation of the conditions and requirements of the task. New formulations indicate new properties of the original objects. 4. Overcoming functional rigidity. You should abandon traditional methods of solving a problem if they turn out to be unsuitable in a particular case, and look for new ways. 5. Comparison of the results of actions at each stage of the decision with the initial conditions [23]. Convergent technologies, along with the development of theoretical thinking, as well as lateral ones, are aimed at moral education. The formation of moral and semantic

constructs and social attitudes, carried out within the framework of collective activity, is aimed at developing the internality of the individual in relation to the objects of social reality. Convergent technologies can be presented in the form of collective creative activities, workshops, etc. The most commonly used form is a problem lesson.

Social-psychological and psychological-pedagogical patterns determine personalized learning as a system. Being basic psychological laws, they find their implementation in the construction of personalized learning in the form of a psychological model, which includes the psychological types of teachers and students, personal developmental pedagogical interaction and personalized learning technologies.

Understanding the theoretical foundations of individualization, personalization and personification of education allows us to conclude: a new organization of education is needed as a process of providing a child with different educational opportunities and organizing his choice from different offers of his individual direction of education and the method of receiving it. An adult becomes the organizer of such an educational space for students and an accompaniment in decision making.

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